

TEACHING ENGLISH IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS THROUGH 4 METHODS: AUDITORY, KINESTHETIC, READING WRITING AND VISUAL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6167219>

Abstract: Nowadays, the problem of developing creative abilities in adolescents is especially relevant in the process of teaching English. In the modern context of the pedagogical process of secondary schools, this is an important scientific problem of historical, ethnic, cultural and socio-pedagogical significance. One of the main tasks of educators is to know in which direction the student learns quickly, in which method he is interested and motivated in learning, in which direction he wants to study. Being able to engage the student also depends on the skill of the educator. Knowing the opinion of the student, working with them in a friendly way, what methods and directions to use in learning English should also be done using appropriate methods.

Key words: creative abilities, modern technology, kinesthetic, visual, reading writing, auditory, speaking skills, games, motivation, methods.

Introduction

The educator who goes to work in any educational institution must first reach the level of a good communicator, a psychologist, with students. It is the duty of every educator to be able to love the student, to teach him the spirit of patriotism, lovingly relying on the idea of national independence. Since the independence of our country, the attention to the teaching and learning of foreign languages has been expanding and developing. In particular, the resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On further improving the system of learning foreign languages" adopted in 2012. Since that day, English has been taught regularly in all schools of the country. Keeping pace with the times, learning the language the world is learning will also help the developing country to develop further.

Main body

There are methods of teaching and learning in English that are designed and put into practice based on the learner's ability and interest.

Kinesthetic learners

How to recognize kinesthetic learners in your class: Kinesthetic learners, sometimes called tactile learners, learn through experiencing or doing things.

They like to get involved by acting out events or using their hands to touch and handle in order to understand concepts. These types of learners might struggle to sit still and often excel at sports or like to dance. They may need to take more frequent breaks when studying.

Auditory learners

How to recognize auditory learners in your class: Auditory learners tend to learn better when the subject matter is reinforced by sound. These students would much rather listen to a lecture than read written notes, and they often use their own voices to reinforce new concepts and ideas. These types of learners prefer reading out loud to themselves. They aren't afraid to speak up in class and are great at verbally explaining things. Additionally, they may be slower at reading and may often repeat things a teacher tells them.

Visual learners

How to recognize visual learners in your class: Someone with a preference for visual learning is partial to seeing and observing things, including pictures, diagrams, written directions and more. This is also referred to as the "spatial" learning style. Students who learn through sight understand information better when it's presented in a visual way. These are your doodling students, your list makers and your students who take notes.

Reading/writing learners

How to recognize reading/writing learners in your class: According to the VARK Modalities theory developed by Fleming and Mills in 1992, reading/writing learners prefer to learn through written words. While there is some overlap with visual learning, these types of learners are drawn to expression through writing, reading articles or books, writing in diaries, looking up words in the dictionary and searching the internet for just about everything.

Now we will learn how to apply these learning methods in the classroom, how effective they are, how easy it is to teach. Today, in order to further develop the teaching of foreign languages not only in schools, but also in kindergartens, lyceums, colleges and higher education institutions, various methods and teaching methods are being introduced using foreign standards. And all specialists and teachers working in these fields are tasked with the study of foreign languages, obtaining certificates of foreign languages, and various benefits are created for them to obtain such degrees. The purpose of encouraging developing youth and teachers, all employees in the field of economics, science and culture to learn foreign languages is to develop the country, to make the country one of the developed countries. As classes grow in schools, textbooks become more difficult, and so do language learning has own stages and challenges.

Language learning is relatively easier in young children than in adults. Because young children have such a psychology that they have a tendency to learn a language more and faster than adults. Criticism, learning by hand, asking a lot of questions, and a high level of curiosity are also clear proofs of this. Another major reason is that young children have a lot of time to learn a language. Young children need to be taught language in the primary grades through a variety of games, word memorization, exercises and songs. When they are taught grammar from primary school, they become bored and tired of the language they are learning, and as a result, the child becomes tired. Because they do not understand the meaning of language, they perceive it mechanically. In terms of child psychology, there are some difficult aspects to teaching them a language. Therefore, every educator should use methods that are as easy and effective as possible, relying on their own knowledge and experience. For example, the following methods can be used to teach language to young children: Singing, acting in accordance with the song, both increases the physical activity of the reader, and hearing the words in English, the ear becomes more organized, and the memorization and pronunciation of these words increases even more. Another way is to memorize short poems. In this case, the student's memory remains the word memorized and the way it is pronounced. This method is called the auditory method in science. Through this method, pupils development becomes very successful, fast, and easy. Another way is for pupils to watch short cartoons in the language they are learning. Children may not understand the English words used in the cartoon, but the words used by the cartoon characters during the expense will automatically be remembered by the child and they will try to repeat, thereby understanding how they act when they say that word. Both the pronunciation of the word and the memorization of the word are very effective after this method. Another method is for children to memorize a specific word, animal name, or family member's name. At the same time, placing each memorized word on the children's fingers and singing them in sequence with the help of a song will help them to pronounce the word and use it correctly in all places in the speaking and writing. This method used is called the kinesthetic method. This method also includes the visual method, and at the same time the child's ability to distinguish between sight and fingers is developing. Another important method is to study in visual. In this case, if the teacher has memorized words on the topic of animals to the children, they should stand on the board to demonstrate the movements or sounds of a particular animal to reinforce them, and the sitting children think of these animals in their imaginations and say their English names. This is a great help for children to understand and interpret the English word they are speaking and will further

increase the pupil's interest in word memorization. During language learning, the teacher should always make sure that children do not get bored or tired. One of the main tasks of a language teacher is to be able to create the environment of the language being taught. For example, going for a walk in a garden or an alley and memorizing the English names of the surrounding objects, colors, animals, plants, using them as examples, will be both fun and memorable for children. In the process, children also develop their ability to distinguish objects and distinguish colors. The more new concepts appear in children's brains, the more interested they become in learning those things and their English names. Again, during the trip, children gain information about their taste, appearance, color, and characteristics by tasting the fruit, and learn what the thing they are memorizing is what it is and how it is an educator who wants children to remember the English name of everything should try to develop the child's sensory organs more. In the process of teaching, the educator should teach as much as possible the involvement of children's visual, auditory, auditory, muscular, sensory and sensory organs. The reason is that teaching it through visual aids, colorful pictures, songs, cartoons and actions is more effective than teaching it by saying a simple word. For example, a child eats a banana and speak about its taste, color, smell, and the pupil tries to say it in English and all the pupils hear it. The same process is tried on another student, and when the zolat is repeated, the children are able to distinguish color, fullness, smell, and repeat the repeated situation without difficulty in English. Another effective method of teaching is to explain a particular word with gestures, facial expressions, and allow pupils to memorize them easily. When addressing students, the command, please, to express feelings of satisfaction on the face as well, eliminates the difficulty of understanding and memorizing that word. We know that in our school days, we would write and paste poems or formulas on the walls, doors, windows, and desks of our classrooms to memorize them. Now young children can use the same method to memorize new words. The pupil writes a word on a list that is difficult to memorize and pronounces and hangs it in the place where he or she looks the most, and memorizes the word for at least 1 week.

Conclusion

In short, care should be taken when teaching a foreign language to a child who does not yet fully understand Uzbek. Teaching language to young children should be taught as a fun game or exercise, not as a command or obligation. And through the knowledge of the method and techniques used, it is possible to teach the grammatical part of the language without difficulty, even when it comes to the complex part of language learning. Teaching through a variety of effective

methods will allow all children in the future to easily learn other foreign languages. Depending on the environment, we can conclude that a person who does not know the language may find it difficult to find his or her way in the future and lag behind in development. For example, the great thinker Abu Nasr al-Farabi was fluent in more than 170 languages, was fluent in them, translated works, wrote treatises on works in different languages, and was able to create in the languages he learned. Such an opportunity led the great scholar to study different world sciences and do great deeds, and he always knew that the best way was to acquire knowledge. The great poet Alisher Navoi said: "He who knows the language knows." ("Til bilgan- el biladi"). It means that when you know the language, you know the culture, the people, the way of life of the state of that language, and the rest of the people know you.

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